

Welfare Packages and Staff Performance in Polytechnics in Anambra State South East, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: The study examined welfare packages and staff's performance in selected polytechnics in Anambra state, Nigeria. It identified the types of employee welfare packages that are being enjoyed by staff of the polytechnics, it explored into the relationship between welfare package and staff's performance, and determined ways in which adequate employee welfare can enhance the performance of staff of the selected polytechnics in Anambra state. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The study was guided by three research questions. The population of the study consisted of 1,600 Academic and Non-teaching (non-academic) staff of Anambra state Polytechnics Mgbakwu, Federal Polytechnics Oko, Grundvig Polytechnics Oba. A sample size of 280 was obtained from the population using Borg and Gall's formula. Data was collected from primary and secondary sources. A questionnaire structured on 5point Likert scale was used for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using percentage count, frequency and mean based on data related to the research questions and the Pearson Correlation. The results of the study showed that the employee welfare packages enjoyed by the staff of the selected polytechnics in Anambra state are Educational promotion programmes, Capacity building Programmes and Subsidized transport fare. The study revealed that adequate employee welfare packages could enhance staff performance by promoting staff job commitment and satisfaction as well as enhance productivity and efficiency in the utilization of resources. The study recommended that there should be continuous provisions for staff welfare packages such that could be so motivating to increase work morale and increase employees' work efficiency among staff of Polytechnics in Anambra state.

KEYWORDS: Academic and Non-academic Staff, Employee Welfare, Performance, Polytechnics.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Employees are the backbone of every organization/company and the happiness of these employees determines their productivity level. A satisfied worker is a motivated employee and a motivated employee is a happy and productive person (Akintunde as cited in Ufoaroh, Udemezue & Anyadufu, 2019). In this era of Globalization, the success of an organization depends on employees' performance. Employees' performance is an essential requirement if an organization is to maintain its efforts towards the realization of predesigned goals (Daddie et al., (2018). Kelekun and Adewole, (2020) opined that, employees in all institutions or organizations should be motivated through welfare package so as to continue to perform their statutory duties. They maintained that welfare packages are expected to be inducing enough for the employee to be motivated to attain maximum performance. Employee welfare package, provided other than wages or salary, could assist in improving and comforting employee. Many staff of the Polytechnics in Anambra State are performing below expectations. Most of the staff do not come to work regularly and even when they do, they are always late to work. They seem not to be satisfied with their job. Their working environment is not conducive and adequate facilities are not provided to motivate them to improve their job performance. Adequate incentives and welfare packages seem not to be provided by their employers. Some employees augment their income from two or three different places of work but they are still not getting job satisfaction and do not enjoy financial freedom. Some employees are owed backlog of allowances as well as their promotion arrears and other benefits to which they are entitled (Poi 2020). This situation demoralizes staff and makes them lose interest in their jobs. It is against this background that the researchers carried out this study.

1.2 Statement of Problem

Employee welfare has been relevant in recent times for greater achievement of desired goals of various organizations. The importance of a satisfied employee cannot be overemphasized. There is the need to provide a good working environment, staff

quarters or accommodation, health care services, safety and appropriate remuneration. Motivation of staff goes a long way in lifting their spirit and morale towards the success of the organization, failure of organizations to adequately take the welfare of their staff into consideration could lead to poor performance and low productivity. It is based on this that the researchers decided to delve into this research.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the following are the objectives:

To identify the types of employee welfare packages that are enjoyed by staff of the selected polytechnics

To ascertain the nature of relationship between welfare package and employee performance

To determine ways in which adequate employee welfare can enhance the performance of Polytechnics in Anambra state

1.4 Research Questions

What are the types of staff welfare packages enjoyed by staff of the selected polytechnics

What is the nature of relationship between welfare package and employee performance

What are the ways in which adequate employee welfare can enhance the performance of Polytechnics in Anambra state

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Welfare

The term welfare as stated by Itodo & Abang,(2018) refers to a predetermine comprehensive list of service, benefits and facilities that supports plan to provide a more comfortable work environment. Daddie et al.,(2018) defined welfare as the state of well being and implies wholesomeness of the human being. It is a desirable state of existence involving the mental, physical, moral and emotional factor of a person. Adequate levels of earnings, safe and humane conditions of work and access to some minimum social security benefits are the major qualitative dimensions of employment which enhance quality of life of workers and their productivity (Daddie et al., 2018).Employee welfare includes anything done for the comfort and improvement of employees that is not covered by their wages (Makanjuola, Shaibu, and Isijola, 2013 as cited in Akintoye and Oforbruku, 2022). Employee welfare could be viewed as the efforts that management puts in place to make life worth living for employees of an organization (Abu, 2016). Poi, (2020), maintained that employee welfare involves the provisions of various services, facilities and amenities for the benefit of the employees for improved standard of living.

2.1.1 Types of Employee Welfare Programmes

The types of benefits being produced for employees are numerous and differ from one organization to another and in varying names.

The types of benefits are divided into five (5) categories:

- For added leisure and income
- For personal identification and participation
- For employment security
- For health protection
- For old age and retirement.

2.2 Employee Performance

The word performance may mean different thing to different people depending on the perspective from which one approaches it. It may imply efficiency, economy, results, or return (profits) on investment (Summermatter & Siegel, 2009 as cited in Daddie et al., 2018).

Oforbruku and Yusuf, (2016) opined Performance as the extent to which a company or firm, as a social system with limited resources, is able to achieve its objectives without depleting its resources and means or putting undue strain on her employees.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The theories which this work was anchored on are the Adams Equity theory of motivation and the Herzberg two factor theory

2.3.1 Adams' Equity Theory of Motivation

This theory was propounded by Adams, according to this theory, employees who believe they get more out of their jobs than what they put into them will be satisfied. Certain aspects of the job shape how an employee perceives it as well. Employees compare their

input output ratio to that of other employees, and if they believe it is fair, they will be satisfied (Robbins, 2007 as cited in Akintoye, 2022). Employees become dissatisfied and less motivated if they perceive an inequity in their input-outcome ratio in comparison to other employees. So, in bid to remedy the challenges confronting management regarding how to motivate workers to perform assigned tasks in order to meet or exceed established standards, management must understand that the workforce weighs the rewards for jobs and expects equity. Armstrong (2001 as cited in Akintoye 2022) asserts that human behaviour is motivated, goal directed, and difficult to motivate; and that the success of any motivated act is dependent on the extent to which the motivator meets the needs of the individual employees for whom it is intended. People are motivated when they anticipate that a cause of action will result in the achievement of a goal and a valued reward that meets their needs (Armstrong, 2001 as cited in Akintoye 2022); motivated people are those who have clearly defined goals and who engage in actions that they anticipate will result in the achievement of those goals

2.3.2 The Herzberg's two factor theory

The theory which is also referred to as the motivator – hygiene theory was propounded by Fredrick Herzberg in 1959. The theory states that Motivational factors are intrinsic to work itself. They make the work more challenging, enjoyable and rewarding. These factors include achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement, growth possibility and the work itself. On the other hand, the hygiene or dissatisfiers have a preventive quality because workers may not be happy working when the environment, they operate in is not hygienic. However, the good hygiene in their work environment does not necessarily guarantee happiness. Rather, it helps to reduce the feeling of dissatisfaction. The hygiene factors explain the work context and they are established to avoid unnecessary pleasantries in workplace. The hygiene factors include; organizational policy and administration, supervision, salary, working conditions, relationship with supervisors and subordinates, status and security.

Employees are expected to enjoy certain conditions of service as a result of the traditional work relationship between them and their employers. When these conditions sufficiently exist in their workplaces, they perform better to meet the minimum requirements of their job. But failure of the conditions to exist in adequate quantity or their absence will cause employees to be dissatisfied in their work, unhappy and they will be less productive. This situation will reduce their level of motivation and may cause them to be ineffective in their job performance. This theory highlights the importance of employee welfare in job performance. Its proposition is that employee welfare is directly related to employee performance. This theory works well when they have same objective of better welfare for both employers and employees.

2.4 Empirical Review

Olatunji, Olufemi, and Omotayo, (2021) investigated the Effects of Fringe Benefits on Employees Productivity in Selected Food and Beverages Production Companies in Ogun State, Nigeria. Questionnaire was the major instrument adopted for this study, a total of 210 respondents were sampled from three food and beverages production organizations. Data generated through the questionnaires for the study were analyzed making use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The results showed that highly competitive fringe benefits have impetus for ensuring drastic reduction in labor turnover. Strong fringe benefits were therefore established to be correlated with employees' motivation on the job, job satisfaction; job performance, employee retention and that proper workplace environment helps in reducing the rate of absentees. The study therefore submitted that application of fringe benefits facilitates effective productivity, while it was also discovered that employees' involvement in organization activities contribute to organizational stability. The two hypotheses tested thus showed a significant relationship between employees' involvement in policy formulation and implementation on individual productivity as well as organizational performance (F Statistic (17.65) $P < 0.05$ and sig. $P < 0.05$) and that a significant relationship exists between application of fringe benefits and individual productivity, as well as organizational performance (F Statistic (8.982) and sig. $P < 0.05$

Ekere and Chima, (2021) conducted a research on employee welfare practices and work performance of the oil & -gas industry in south Nigeria. The target population comprises of Oil and Gas companies in Southern Nigeria while the accessible population is made up of 165 employees from 5 major Oil and Gas companies in southern Nigeria. The accessible population was selected using purposive and sampling techniques. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents via email and personal contacts out of which 143 copies representing 86.4% were correctly filled and used for further analyses. Hence, the study concludes that employee welfare practices have a positive relationship with work performance and thus recommends that Oil and Gas companies should give more attention to employee welfare to facilitate work performance.

Poi (2020) examined employee welfare packages and ways in which they can promote the performance of public organizations in Rivers State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of the study consisted of the 15,600 civil servants in Rivers State. A sample size of 780 civil servants comprising of 400 males and 380 females was drawn through stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire titled; "Employee Welfare Packages and Organizational Performance Questionnaire (EWPOPQ)" was designed by the researcher and was used for data collection. The instrument which contained 23 items was properly validated and a reliability of 0.81 was obtained through Cronbach Alpha approach. Percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study showed that the employee welfare packages enjoyed by civil servants in Rivers State included rent subsidy and transport allowance but they were less than expected. The study revealed that adequate employee welfare packages could enhance staff performance by promoting job commitment and satisfaction as well as enhance productivity and efficiency in the utilization of resources. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the Rivers State Government should implement adequate welfare packages such as the new minimum wage and ensure that she upholds the agreements reached with labor unions in the state to avoid adverse industrial actions.

Munywoki, and Kariuki, (2020) examined the influence of perceived employee welfare programs on employee job satisfaction at Kenya Railways Corporation. The study had a target population of 1,214, being all the employees of Kenya Railways, MGR Operations. A sample size of 123 employees was established by use of a multistage stratified random sampling method. The study used a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. Primary data was obtained using a structured self administered questionnaire. Analysis of data used regression analysis. The study determined a statistically significant connection between employee welfare programs and employee job satisfaction at Kenya Railways Corporation. Employee health programs exhibited the highest influence on employee job satisfaction trailed by flexible work programs. This study has contributed to the theory of job satisfaction and supplemented existing literature in employee welfare programs by establishing correlations between employee welfare programs tested in the study and employee job satisfaction.

Akintoye and Ofobruku, (2022) examined the influence of staff welfare package has on organizational performance. The discourse, established from the analyzed literatures that staff welfare package increases staff motivation, while staff motivation on the other hand increases and brings about productivity. Also, the paper assumes that there is a sparse volume of literatures on effects of staff welfare package specifically on organizational performance. The study therefore concludes that while more empirical work needs to be done specifically on the effects of staff welfare package on organizational performance, it can be inferred from previous findings as follows: if staff welfare package leads to motivation, and staff motivation leads to higher productivity; it, therefore, follows that staff welfare package impacts organizational performance. Recommendations were made that employers should let go of the entitlement attitude; the staff should be granted a welfare package of value; the employers should follow the tenets of equity and fair welfare; and the staff should strive to know their rights and privileges.

Ufoaroh, Udemezue, and Anyadufu, (2019), carried out a study on Employee Welfare Package and its Impact on Productivity in Roesons Industries Ltd Enugu-Ukwu, Anambra State, Nigeria. The researchers sourced their data from two sources which are primary and secondary sources. The company under-study has a population of 42 employees and the population was adopted as the sampling size due to their small figure. Properly constructed questionnaires were administered to the respondents of which all were completely answered and returned. The descriptive statistical method was used to analyze the data to determine their mean, range, standard deviations etc. These were further helped by tables showing questions from the questionnaire, the Yes response and No response with their percentages. The correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between the two responses/variables while goodness-of-fit statistical analysis was used to test and validate the significance of the responses/variables. This research study shows that the productivity level of any employee depends on the welfare package available to him/her. In other words, a highly motivated worker is a highly productive worker as observed from this research

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the survey design. Survey instrument for the collection of data was developed for the study using a 5-point likert scale for each item in the questionnaire

3.2 Area of Study

The area of the study is Anambra State, South-East Nigeria. Its state theme is “Light Of The Nation”. It has twenty one local government areas; it is an igbo speaking state. This zone is an agricultural zone and the people are predominantly farmers and traders. Its boundaries are formed by Delta state to the west, Imo state to the south, Enugu state to the east and kogi state to the north.

3.3 Sources of Data

In the course of carrying out the research, two sources were used to gather the needed data. These include; primary and secondary sources of data.

3.3.1 Primary Source of Data.

The primary data was collected from systematically constructed questionnaires that were administered to the study sample of academic and non- academic staff of selected Polytechnics in Anambra state. Primarily data collected were a representation of facts, observations, and occurrences in which the researchers was the original collector.

3.3.2 Secondary Source of Data

Secondary data comprised of existing materials from books, archives, and public offices. To gather the necessary information needed for the study; the above sources were used by the researchers, the internet was surfed for current books and Journals.

3.4 Population of the Study

The target population for the study was the academic and non academic staff of selected polytechnics in Anambra state, south-east, Nigeria. A population of 1600 staff working in the three (3) selected polytechnics in Anambra state. The Polytechnics used for the study include; Federal Polytechnic Oko (OKO POLY), Anambra state Polytechnic Mgbakwu (ANSPOLY), and the Grundvig Polytechnics Oba. The researchers selected these institutions based on their activeness and popularity in the state.

3.5 Determination of the Sample Size

The sample size for this study was determined using the Borg & Gall formular of (1973). Statistically, the Borg &Gall (1973) formula for sample size is given by

$$n = (Zx)^2(e) [N]$$

$$(Zx)^2 = \text{Confidence level at } 0.05$$

$$e = \text{Error of margin (0.05)}$$

$$N = \text{Population of Interest } = 2600$$

$$X = \text{Significance Level}$$

Substituting in the formula, we have:

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [1600]$$

$$= 3.8416 \times 80$$

$$n = 307$$

$$\text{Sample size } = 307$$

3.5.1 Quota Sampling Technique

The quota sampling technique was used to determine the proportion of the respondents for each institution selected for the study. Therefore, the quota for each institution was determined using the Bowley’s Allocation formula.

$$nh = \frac{nN_h}{N}$$

Where

nh = number of units allocated to each sub group

Nh = no of respondent in each sub group

n = Total sample size

N = Total population size

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Table 3.5.1: proportion of population and sample size for each institution

S/N	INSTITUTION	POPULATION	SAMPLE SIZE
1	Federal Poly Oko	1407	$\frac{1407}{1600} \times 307 = 269$
2	Anspoly Mgbakwu	145	$\frac{145}{1600} \times 307 = 28$
3	Grundvig Poly Oba	48	$\frac{48}{1600} \times 307 = 10$
	TOTAL	1600	307

Table 3.5.2 Questionnaire Distribution and Return Rate

S/N	INSTITUTION	NO DISTRIB BUTED	DISTRIB UTED RATE %	NUMBER RETURNE D	RESPON SE RATE %	NUMBER NOT RETURN ED	RESPONSE RATE %
1	Fed Poly Oko	269	88%	242	79%	27	9%
2	Anspoly Oko	28	9%	28	9%	0	0%
3	Grundvig Poly Oba	10	3%	10	3%	0	0%
	TOTAL	307	100	280	91%	27	9%

Source: filed survey, 2023

From table 3.5. 2 above, it is shown that questionnaire totaling 269 with a distribution rate of 88% were distributed in the selected Federal Polytechnic Oko. The number of returned questionnaire was 242 with response rate of 79%. 28 questionnaires with distribution rate of 9% were distributed in Anambra state Polytechnic Mgbakwu, 28 questionnaires with returned rate of 9% were returned. 10 questionnaires with distribution rate of 3% were distributed in Grundvig Poly Oba. The number returned was 10 at the return rate of 3%, In summary, 307 questionnaires were distributed while 280 questionnaires were returned.

Analysis of Questionnaire Demography Data

Table 3.5.3 Summary of the personal data of the 280 respondents

S/N	SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	MALE	121	43%
2	FEMALE	159	57%
	TOTAL	280	100

Source: the demographic variables and their frequencies gotten from questionnaire administered.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed in the study. The descriptive tools include frequency distribution, percentages and mean. Data was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 probability level of significance. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is a widely used statistical method for measuring association between variables.

Research Question One: What are the employee welfare packages enjoyed by staff

ITEMS ON TYPES OF WELFARE PACKAGE ENJOYED BY STAFF								
S/N		SA	A	U	D	SD	MEAN	DECISION
1	My institution provides full educational promotion programmes to all staff	136 680 49%	69 276 24%	12 36 4%	27 54 10%	36 36 13%	3.8	Agreed
2	We benefit from safety and health program	63 315 22%	47 188 17%	16 48 6%	89 178 32%	65 65 23%	2.8	Disagreed
3	My institution has full job security	59 295 22%	51 102 18%	45 135 16%	65 130 23%	60 60 21%	2.5	Disagreed
4	Capacity building programmes for career growth is regularly provided	127 635 45%	63 252 22%	3 9 1%	52 104 19%	35 35 13%	3.7	Agreed
5	We benefit from house allowance in my place of work	43 215 15%	52 208 19%	6 18 2%	108 216 38%	71 71 25%	2.6	Disagreed
6	We enjoy subsidized transport fare	139 695 50%	74 296 26%	2 6 1%	38 76 13%	27 27 10%	3.9	Agreed
7	We enjoy regular salary increment	74 370 26%	58 232 21%	5 15 2%	68 136 24%	75 75 27%	2.9	Disagreed
8	Adequate recreational facilities are provided for staff.	42 210 15%	38 152 14%	24 72 8%	108 216 39%	68 68 24%	2.6	Disagreed
9	We benefit from workers compensation program.	55 275 20%	46 184 16%	8 24 3%	77 154 27%	94 94 34%	2.6	Disagreed
10	funeral services are provided for staff from the institution	34 170 12%	57 228 20%	13 39 5%	78 156 28%	98 98 32%	2.4	Disagreed

Source: researchers' computation from field survey, 2023

Table above showed that out of the 10 items, the respondents agreed on three items (1,4 and 6), and they disagreed on the other 7 items. 73% of the staff of the selected polytechnic with a mean score of 3.8 agreed that the institutions provide full educational promotion programmes to their staff. 67% of the staff with a mean score of 3.7 agreed that the institutions provide capacity building programs for career growth and 76% of the staff agreed that they enjoy subsidized transport fare. Items 1,4 and 6 were the only 3 items with mean set scores of 3.80, 3.70 and 3.90 which were greater than the criterion mean score of 3.0, the remaining 7

items had various mean set scores ranging from 2.40 to 2.90 which were less than the criterion mean of 3.00. Hence the respondents disagreed on them.

Therefore, the Employee welfare packages enjoyed by staff of the selected polytechnics in Anambra state are Educational promotion program Capacity building Programs and Subsidized transport fare. Staff of these polytechnics do not enjoy; safety and health program, house allowance, regular salary increment, adequate recreational facilities, workers compensation program, funeral services and full job security are not enjoyed by the staff of the polytechnics.

Research Question 2: on what is the relationship between welfare package and staff performance

Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Welfare package and Staff performance.

Variables	N	Welfare package	Employee performance	p-value	Decision
Welfare package	280	1	.109	.029	Significant
Staff performance	280	.109	1		

As shown in Table 2, there was a significant relationship between welfare package and employee job satisfaction, $r = .109$, p -value $< .05$. Since the p -value was less than 0.05, This implies that there was a significant relationship between welfare package and employee performance.

Research Question three: In what ways can adequate employee welfare enhance the performance of staff of these polytechnics

ITEMS ON WAYS WELFARE PACKAGE CAN ENHANCE THE PERFORMANCE OF STAFF		SA	A	U	D	SD	MEAN	DECISION
1	Welfare package promotes staff commitment to duties	128 640 46%	72 288 26%	3 9 1%	40 80 14%	37 37 13%	3.7	Agreed
2	It promotes staff job satisfaction	119 595 43%	81 324 29%	- - -	42 84 15%	38 38 13%	3.7	Agreed
3	Employee welfare packages increases the rate of wastefulness among staff	47 235 16%	21 108 9%	5 18 1%	143 286 51%	64 64 23%	2.5	Disagreed
4	Adequate Employee welfare packages give employees a sense of belonging	93 465 33%	113 452 40%	7 21 2%	57 114 20%	10 10 4%	3.8	Agreed
5	Employee welfare package reduces the ability of employees to save money	15 75 5%	10 40 4%	8 24 3%	186 372 66%	61 61 22%	2.0	Disagreed
6	It increases Employee retention	149 798 56%	52 208 19%	- - -	47 94 16%	32 32 11%	4.0	Agreed
7	It enhances efficiency in the utilization of available resources.	88 440 31%	109 436 39%	7 21 2%	20 40 8%	56 56 20%	3.5	Agreed
8	It increases the rate of employee turnover intention	21 105 8%	33 132 11%	27 81 10%	43 86 15%	156 156 55%	2.0	Disagreed

9	Employee welfare packages make employees life worth living.	153	71	9	17	30	4.0	Agreed
		760	284	27	34	30		
		54%	25%	3%	6%	10%		
10	It increases the rate of disloyalty among staff	27	23	31	80	119	2.1	Disagreed
		135	92	93	160	119		
		10%	9%	11%	28%	42%		

Source: Researchers computations from field, 2023.

The above Table 3 shows that out of the 10 items on ways adequate employee welfare enhances the performance of staff of these polytechnics the respondents agreed on 6 of them. They agreed on items 1, 2, 4, 6, 7 and 9 which had weighted mean set scores of 3.7, 3.7, 3.8, 4.0, 3.5, 4.0 that were greater than the criterion mean of 3.0. Also, over 65% of the respondents agreed on these items. Items 3, 5, 8 and 10 had weighted mean set scores of 2.5, 2.0, 2.0, and 2.1 which are less than the criterion mean of 3.0 and they were disagreed upon by the respondents.

Therefore, the ways in which adequate employee welfare packages can enhance the performance of staff of polytechnics in Anambra state include the following; it promotes staff commitment to duty, staff job satisfaction, it gives employees a sense of belonging, increases, it increases employee retention, it enhances efficiency in the utilization of available resources and Employee welfare packages make employees' life worth a living.

4.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In the preceding section of this chapter, the researcher presented and analyzed the results of this study using the research questions of the study as a guide

Research question one on what are the types of welfare packages enjoyed, the employee welfare packages enjoyed by staff of the selected polytechnics in Anambra state were ;Educational promotion programs, Capacity building Programs and Subsidized transport fare. These items have mean scores above 3.0 which is greater than the criterion mean. This finding is in line with the observation in Waititu, et al., (2017), Moruli, et al.,(2018) who stated that, there are various aspects of welfare benefits that are used in improving the performance of workers at work place. Among of these aspects are: health package, policies based on the salary and other benefits, training and development.

The second hypothesis one was tested with Correlation to explore the relationship between welfare package and staff performance of selected polytechnics in Anambra state. The result showed that welfare package have significant relationship with (r = .109, p = .029, p-value < .05) staff performance in Anambra state South-East, Nigeria. This finding is in line with the observation of Aslpoor and Amirnejad (2016) who contended that, services such as salary bonus, health allowances, transport allowances and security insurance make employee to devote their maximum capacity in their respective responsibilities and hence delivering service on time.

The third research question on what ways welfare package can enhance staff performance of the selected polytechnics in Anambra state. Therefore, the ways in which adequate employee welfare packages can enhance the performance of staff of polytechnics in Anambra state include the following; it promotes staff commitment to duty, staff job satisfaction, it gives employees a sense of belonging, it increases employee retention, it enhances efficiency in the utilization of available resources and Employee welfare packages make employees' life worth living. The findings imply that, having various welfare benefits in the organization can enhance employees' performance. This is not only researcher's opinion, but also the opinions of other scholars such as Waitituet al (2017), Musyoka (2015) who stated that, there are various aspects of welfare benefits that are used to improve the performance of workers at work place

Summary

The study findings revealed that, there are various types of welfare benefits provided at the selected polytechnics in Anambra state south east, Nigeria. These benefits are Educational promotion programs, Capacity building Programs and Subsidized transport fare. Majority of respondents strongly agreed that welfare benefits enhance staff performance, through promoting staff commitment to duty, staff job satisfaction, giving employees a sense of belonging, increasing employee retention, enhancing efficiency in the utilization of available resources and making employees' life worth a living

Recommendations

The researchers recommend that for effective staff performance in polytechnics, the management should continually make provisions for staff welfare such that could be so motivating to increase work morale and increase employees' work efficiency.

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